

Role Of Monitoring And Evaluation System In Institutional Development At Secondary Level In Punjab

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Development, School, Monitoring System, Researchers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4966372</p>	<p><i>This research paper focuses on the Role of Monitoring and Evaluation System in Institutional Development at Secondary Level in Punjab. To explore role of monitoring in institutional development with respect to teachers' attendance, students' enrolment, educational facilities, was main objective of the study. Quantitative design was used for which survey was conducted to collect the data. The study was delimited to the district Rawalpindi of province Punjab. Out of 334 headmasters, one hundred secondary school level head teachers of Rawalpindi district were randomly selected as a sample of the study. Two self-developed questionnaires, one for headmasters of public schools and other for Monitoring & Evaluation Assistants, were used as data collection tools after pretesting for reliability and taking suggestions of three experts for validity purpose. Cronbach Alpha values of questionnaire for headmasters was 0.80 and it was 0.82 for questionnaire for Monitoring & Evaluation Assistants. It was found that majority of both type of respondents heads as well as monitoring and evaluation experts was of the view that there is vital role played by monitoring system in institutional development at secondary school level. Training of Monitoring Staff, improvement in the system and further research studies on different areas and aspects of the system were recommended by the researchers.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

Sufficient, demanding, comprehensive and uninterrupted monitoring and supervision are one of the most imperative keys to effective execution of any educational program. When any educational program comes into operation there arises the need for some kind of tool by which the improvement of application can be eagerly assessed. Such instrument is commonly known as mechanism of monitoring. In every system of education, inspection and supervision activities are covered by monitoring. (Khwaja, 2017, Rehman, 2018). Monitoring encompasses practice of gathering information and occasionally accumulating significant signs to assess input and output and procedure to give on the function of elements of the educational system (Bahadur et al., 2017).

A key instrument of management is monitoring which delivers the primary data about the operation of any program or any project (Peter, 2017). To examine the smooth functioning of every program, every institute and system develops its own mechanism of monitoring (Mohanty, 2015). Some administrations depend on inside monitoring (conducted by officers within the organization for it is responsibility of every administrator to observe the activities of its assistants and implementation of the program) whereas others rely on outward monitoring (it is done by a third party (Daft, 2017, Bahadur et al, 2017). Monitoring is procedure of intermittent check on dimensions of programme's input, and activities and output undertaken during programme application (Bashaugi, 2019).

According to KIPA (2011), there are numerous techniques of providing material and data concerning with the subject of monitoring, but the most operative methods of it are measured as contribution in classes, and institutional facilities, monitoring the learning procedure or doings which take place.

Monitoring has very vital position in managing active achievement of the organizational system. Monitoring is pivot component of administration as it tracks all concerning progress and it facilitates and supports effective decision making (Lazaridou & Beeka, 2015). Hence, it is prerequisite and essential of every organization. Nearly every well-known organization in the world has either its own system of monitoring or it is done by hiring monitoring services from 3rd parties as World Bank or UNICEF (World Bank, 2018).

Fullan (2015) stated that the monitoring is the constant assemblage of the information to examine the prevalent system and to yield procedure to convey modification in it. Instead, evaluation is a vast as it is frequently used to scrutinize the efficiency of the system and to deliver decision making about the improvement, development and its impact (Rengasaemy, 2017). So the both are for same ultimate purpose and these are used in series, one gives information whereas the other uses that information altering into information and gives value (Williams, 2016).

Shamiand Aisha (2007) and Shami& Sabir (2007) described following goals of monitoring:

1. Confirmation about input, activities and output are going according to pre-planning.
2. Preparation of records of activities, input and output.
3. Provision of results whether these are in sequence with pre-planned targets or in contrast with pre-planned targets.
4. Assist administrators to decide accurately and take decisions.

In Schools of the Punjab, Monitoring and Evaluation System had been introduced to improve the education system. To what extent it is meeting the target, to find out the answer of this question, current study was conducted by the researchers.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The Program Monitoring and Implementation Unit is monitoring the public schools of the Punjab since its establishment on the indicators like teachers' presence, students' attendance, cleanliness, missing facilities and funds utilization. And the schools are being evaluated on same indicators in terms of percentage. Hence this study was conducted to analyze the Role of Monitoring and Evaluation System in Institutional Development at Secondary level in Punjab.

OBJECTIVES

1. To explore role of monitoring in institutional development with respect to teachers' attendance, students' enrolment, educational facilities.
2. To give suggestions for improvement of monitoring system.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Monitoring of a system is straight related to the administration and its success and accomplishment. Systematic monitoring may increase standard and of education. Constant regular monitoring is an indispensable element of any institute and it is accountable for improving the standard of the institute. Owing to the need of monitoring for improving the institutional development, this study would be of great significance for educational administrators heads, teachers and monitoring staff.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Quantitative design was used for which survey was conducted to collect the data. The study was delimited to the district Rawalpindi of province Punjab.

Population

All public secondary schools, all heads and all Monitoring & Evaluation Assistants served as population of study. There were 334 Govt. sector secondary schools in District Rawalpindi.

Sample of the Study

Head Teachers: One hundred Head teachers working in 100 secondary schools of Rawalpindi district were randomly selected as a sample of the study.

Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants: Fifty monitoring and evaluation assistants were selected randomly as second group of sample.

Research Tools

Two self-developed questionnaires, one for headmasters of public schools other for Monitoring & Evaluation Assistants were finalized as data collection tools after pretesting for reliability and taking suggestions of three experts for validity purpose. Cronbach Alpha values of questionnaire for headmasters was 0.83 and it was 0.85 for questionnaire for Monitoring & Evaluation Assistants.

Data Collection

Data were collected in person by researchers.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed by using chi square because it was most appropriate for this type of data. Table value at 0.05 level=9.49 was taken in this research for every table.

DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis of Responses of Head Teachers

Table 1. There is effective role of monitoring in students' enrolment and enrolment of students has increased due to monitoring of education department

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	52	38	0	8	2	110.8
percentages	52	38	0	8	2	

The results of table exhibit that most of headmasters/head teachers (90 %) said that they are satisfied with effective role of monitoring and evaluation. Chi-Square value was 110.8 which was above the table value 9.49. It is clear from head Teachers' responses that they are agreed that there is effective role of monitoring in students' enrolment and enrolment of students has increased due to monitoring of education department.

Table 2. There is positive role of monitoring on teachers' absenteeism and monitoring has lowered the absenteeism of teachers

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	51	31	0	16	2	91.1
percentages	51	31	0	16	2	

The results of this table exhibit that most of headmasters (82 %) said that they are satisfied that monitoring has decreased absenteeism in teachers. Chi-Square value was 91.1 which was above the table value 9.49. It is clear from headmasters' responses that they are agreed that there is positive role of monitoring in teachers' absenteeism and monitoring has lowered the absenteeism of teachers.

Table 3. There is significant role of monitoring in improving educational facilities and educational facilities in schools are going to be fulfilled by monitoring

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	53	35	0	7	5	105.4
percentages	53	35	0	7	5	

The results of above table exhibit that most of headmasters (88 %) were satisfied with positive effect of monitoring on improving educational facilities in schools. Chi-Square value was 105.4 which was above the table value 9.49. It is clear from headmasters' responses that they are agreed that there is significant role of monitoring in improving educational facilities and educational facilities in schools are going to be fulfilled by monitoring.

Table 4. There is vital role of monitoring in improving schools' performance and monitoring team takes remedial measures for improving schools' performance

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	48	36	0	10	6	86.8
percentages	48	36	0	10	6	

Above table exhibits that most of headmasters (84%) were satisfied with effect of monitoring on remedial measures for enhancing school performance. Chi-Square value was 86.8 which was above the table value 179.15. It is clear from headmasters' responses that they are agreed that there is vital role of monitoring in improving schools' performance and monitoring team takes remedial measures for improving schools' performance.

Table 5: Suggestions to improve role of monitoring in institutional development

S. No	Description	%age
1	There is need of skillful and proper training of monitoring staff in order to make role of monitoring more effective	90
2	Monitoring of teachers if done accurately and properly, can play a pivot role in institutional development.	85
5	Teachers should be properly monitored and evaluated in use of traditional methods and latest teaching methods and strategies	80

Table. 5 describes the suggestions given by heads to improve effectiveness of monitoring and to enhance role of monitoring in institutional development. Ninety percent respondents suggested that there is need of skillful and proper training of monitoring staff in order to make role of monitoring more effective. Eighty five percent of respondents suggested that Monitoring of teachers if done accurately and properly can play a pivot role in institutional development. Eighty percent head teachers gave suggestion that there should be proper and appropriate monitoring of teachers and if adequately evaluated in methodology of traditional methods and latest teaching methods and strategies, it can enhance students' performance.

Analysis of Responses of Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants

Table 6. There is effective role of monitoring in students' enrolment and enrolment of students has increased due to monitoring of education department

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	27	20	0	3	0	63.8
percentages	54	40	0	6	0	

The data given in above table indicates that most of monitoring and evaluation assistants (94 %) said that they are satisfied with quality of monitoring and evaluation provided. Chi-Square value was 63.8 which was above the table value 9.49. It is clear from monitoring and evaluation assistants' responses that they are agreed that there is effective role of monitoring in students' enrolment and enrolment of students has increased due to monitoring of education department.

Table 7. There is positive role of monitoring on teachers' absenteeism and monitoring has lowered the absenteeism of teachers

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	28	16	0	6	0	57.6
percentages	56	32	0	12	0	

The data presented in above table shows that most of monitoring and evaluation assistants (88 %) said that they are satisfied that monitoring has decreased absenteeism in teachers. Chi-Square value was 57.6 which was above the table value 9.49. It is clear from monitoring and evaluation assistants' responses that they are agreed that there is positive role of monitoring on teachers' absenteeism and monitoring has lowered the absenteeism of teachers.

Table 8. There is significant role of monitoring in improving educational facilities and educational facilities in schools are going to be fulfilled by monitoring

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	27	18	0	5	0	57.8
percentages	54	36	0	10	0	

This table exhibits that most of monitoring and evaluation assistants (91 %) were satisfied with positive effect of monitoring on improving educational facilities in schools. Chi-Square value was 57.8 which was above the table value 9.49. It is clear from monitoring and evaluation assistants' responses that they are agreed that there is significant role of monitoring in improving educational facilities and educational facilities in schools are going to be fulfilled by monitoring.

Table 9. There is vital role of monitoring in improving schools' performance and monitoring team takes remedial measures for improving schools' performance

	SA	A	UND	DA	SDA	Chi Square
Frequency	25	18	0	6	1	48.6
percentages	4	7	0	48	41	

The results of this table exhibit that most of monitoring and evaluation assistants (88.5 %) were satisfied with effect of monitoring on remedial measures for enhancing school performance. Chi-Square value was 48.6 which was above the table value 179.15. It is clear from monitoring and evaluation assistants' responses that they are agreed that there is vital role of monitoring in improving schools' performance and monitoring team takes remedial measures for improving schools' performance.

Table 10: Suggestions to improve role of monitoring in institutional development

S. No	Description	%age
1	Number of monthly visits of monitoring staff per school be increased.	95
3	Monitoring should cover all aspects school including teaching in classrooms.	90
4	To meet the needs of modern time, there is urgent need of proper and undated skilled training of Monitoring staff.	85
5	Government and administration should give incentives and some necessary facilities to monitoring and evaluation staff, in this way their dedication and motivation will be enhanced.	85
6	There should be also monitoring of teachers regarding their teaching, teaching competencies and teaching methodology with respect to traditional as well as latest methods of teaching.	80

Data presented in this table narrates the opinions given by monitoring staff to improve effectiveness of monitoring and to enhance role of monitoring in institutional development. It was suggested by ninety five percent respondents that number of monthly visits of monitoring staff per school be increased. Ninety percent respondents suggested

monitoring should cover all aspects school including teaching in classrooms. Eighty five percent respondents suggested that to meet the needs of modern time, there is urgent need of proper and undated skilled training of Monitoring staff. Eighty five percent respondents suggested that government and administration should give incentives and some necessary facilities to monitoring and evaluation staff, in this way their dedication and motivation will be enhanced. Eighty percent respondents suggested that there should be also monitoring of teachers regarding their teaching, teaching competencies and teaching methodology with respect to traditional as well as latest methods of teaching.

CONCLUSIONS

Majority of heads was of the view that there is effective role of monitoring in students' enrolment and enrolment of students has increased due to monitoring of education department, there is positive role of monitoring on teachers' absenteeism and monitoring has lowered the absenteeism of teachers, there is significant role of monitoring in improving educational facilities and educational facilities in schools are going to be fulfilled by monitoring, there is vital role of monitoring in improving schools' performance and monitoring team takes remedial measures for improving schools' performance.

It is clear from monitoring and evaluation assistants' responses that they are agreed that there is effective role of monitoring in students' enrolment and enrolment of students has increased due to monitoring of education department, there is positive role of monitoring on teachers' absenteeism and monitoring has lowered the absenteeism of teachers, There is significant role of monitoring in improving educational facilities and educational facilities in schools are going to be fulfilled by monitoring. There is vital role of monitoring in improving schools' performance and monitoring team takes remedial measures for improving schools' performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. There is need of skillful and proper training of monitoring staff (in collaboration with the education and monitoring and evaluation departments of Punjab) in order to make role of monitoring more effective.
2. Monitoring should also focus on teaching. Monitoring of teachers' performance, if done accurately and properly, can play a pivot role in institutional development. Therefore, the monitoring strategy and scope should be expanded from physical aspects to the pedagogical aspects of teachers' performance. In other words, monitoring should cover all aspects school including teaching in classrooms. As ninety percent respondents suggested that monitoring staff should be well trained in order to cope with demands of modern era.
3. As per suggestion collected from the respondents, the number of monthly visits of monitoring staff per school be increased.
4. Incentives and other facilities be given to monitoring and evaluation staff in order to enhance their motivation and performance regarding unbiased and neutral monitoring and evaluation.
5. This research study was conducted only at secondary school level, which may be conducted at other levels of education e.g. elementary, higher secondary or higher levels of education as well as other districts of the province and other provinces too.

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